

Simulating stress in urban active mobility: A multimodal framework integrating physiological and mobile eye tracking data in cycling

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Abstract. To foster sustainable urban mobility, it is critical to design cycling infrastructure that is not only physically safe but also perceived as such. Traditional methods for assessing cycling experiences, i.e., accident statistics and surveys, often fail to capture the dynamic, real-time interactions between a cyclist and the surrounding environment. This paper presents a novel methodology that combines mobile eye tracking with stress measurements derived from wearable physiological sensors for an integrated agent-based modelling framework that provides a deeper understanding of cyclist behaviour under stressful conditions. To validate the feasibility of our approach, a pilot field study was conducted in Salzburg, Austria, where participants navigated two distinct routes of varying cycling infrastructure. Preliminary results demonstrate a quantifiable link between inadequate infrastructure and elevated stress levels. Participants on the more complex route exhibited a higher number of Moment of Stress (MOS) events, which coincided with their self-reported feedback. Leveraging geo-referenced stress measurements, we identified spatial clusters of stress (hotspots) around intersections with high traffic volumes and road crossings, which were most prominent on the "difficult" route, which lacks adequate mobility infrastructure. Our research offers an empirically informed methodology for designing and evaluating infrastructure that prioritises safety and well-being of cyclists.

Keywords: Cycling stress · Urban mobility · Eye tracking · Physiological sensor measurements · Spatial analysis · Computer vision · Agent-based modelling

1 Introduction

Confronted with intensifying climate change and the detrimental effects of car-centric urban design, municipalities around the globe are increasingly turning to active transportation. Cycling, as an equitable and accessible mode of transport, is at the forefront of this movement. Despite benefits such as reduced carbon emissions and improved physical health (20; 21), the adoption of cycling faces a critical obstacle: the perception of safety and stress associated with navigating urban environments.

While research shows that physically separated cycling paths and painted bike lanes have a positive effect on perceived safety, interactions between mobility users on shared roads remain a major source of conflict (1). To design urban spaces that are intuitively safe and comfortable for cyclists of all ages and abilities, multimodal data collections are required to evaluate dynamic experiences encountered during cycling activities (12). A central challenge lies in understanding cyclists' individualistic experiences. By combining mobile eye tracking and physiological sensors, we can unlock insights that reveal not just where and when cyclists feel stressed, but how and why they perceive an environment as stressful. Highly granular sensor data on an individual level provides the evidence base for a user-centred approach to urban mobility design.

Real-world environments contain a variety of confounding factors that make it difficult to isolate specific stress determinants in cycling activities. By modelling urban characteristics within an agent-based simulation framework and integrating observed mobility user behaviour identified in real-world studies, spatial simulation can act as a controlled environment that mimics real-world perceptions in active mobility. This allows for a systematic analysis and identification of specific environmental elements that contribute to individual stress situations, while controlling for confounding effects such as high traffic volumes during rush hours. By using agent-based models (ABMs) in the context of urban (mobility) planning, policymakers are able to test different design options in a virtual setting before implementing them in real-world infrastructure (6). In our study, agent behaviours are parameterised directly from multimodal sensor measurements that were collected in real-world urban cycling environments, providing empirical data that can be implemented within the simulation model. While ABMs cannot predict beyond their inputs, our empirically informed approach provides a realistic and practical tool for assessing how changes to infrastructure and varying confounding factors impact cyclist stress and safety.

2 Motivation and Research Goal

Cyclist safety remains a significant public health issue and urban design challenge. In urban areas cyclist collisions and near-misses are not only frequent but also under-reported (7). Quantifying perceived safety through real-time stress measurements and identifying stress triggers in urban environments supports evidence-based mobility policies and targeted improvement of cycling infrastructure, contributing to healthier and more sustainable cities. Transportation planners often rely on accident statistics, surveys, and self-reported feedback to study cyclist behaviour (11). These traditional approaches come with limitations, as statistics are reactive instead of predictive, and surveys tend to be subjective and biased (19; 11). Hence, they fail to capture the dynamic and unpredictable nature of cycling experiences. Standard procedures developed for controlled laboratory experiments are equally inadequate for capturing the complexities of real-world conditions (17). To simulate naturalistic behaviour of cyclists and interactions between road users, empirically collected data on individuals' involuntary body

responses are needed. Based on wearable sensor measurements, relevant features can be extracted and used to understand the subconscious behaviour through visual attention and physiological stress (10; 16; 15).

Cycling experiences are not only about observations; they are frequently tied to personal feelings, which are influenced by past experiences (13) where mobility users perceived stress. Hence, identifying these stress situations is essential for human-centred mobility planning. Physiological sensor data has shown to be a valid data source for an objective assessment of acute stress (1). Leveraging state-of-the-art stress detection methodologies to identify Moment of Stress (MOS) events (16; 15) through filtered electrodermal activity (EDA) measurements, one can identify *when* stress situations were experienced. Geo-referencing these stress events through GPS data provides information on *where* stress was experienced. Linking this information with external data sources such as OpenStreetMap (OSM) and visual cues extracted from eye tracking data, i.e., blink rate, frequency and duration of fixations, and motion speed, MOS events can be contextualised and attributed to individual objects or infrastructure (8).

Considering the multitude of stress factors encountered in active mobility (24; 3; 11), this preliminary study aims to investigate physiological and self-reported stress, based on the availability of targeted mobility infrastructure. An ABM implements empirically collected physiological data and mimics changes in cyclists viewing behaviour under changing environmental surroundings and stressful cycling conditions. By collecting and integrating multimodal data sources, we establish empirically grounded inputs for an agent-based simulation model designed to reproduce dynamic cycling experiences. Specifically, we introduce an empirical framework for capturing cyclists' real-world experiences in which variations in physiological and visual responses elicited under stressful cycling conditions are incorporated into the ABM to modulate simulated road dynamics. Furthermore, we investigate the feasibility of mobile eye tracking technologies for detecting stress in naturalistic cycling environments.

3 Methodology

To investigate interactions between cyclists and their surrounding environment, we propose an integrated approach that combines an empirical multimodal user study with street layout and features extracted from OSM to develop an agent-based simulation model of cyclist behaviour under varying road conditions (Fig. 1).

As the first step, we conducted a pilot study under real-world cycling conditions, where study participants followed two predetermined routes within Salzburg, Austria (Fig. 2). 10 students (5 female and 5 male, average age 25) from the University of Salzburg volunteered to participate in the experiment. Each student was randomly assigned to one of the test routes (Fig. 3): **Group 1** navigated a route characterised by high-quality, dedicated cycling infrastructure and minimal obstacles (**easy route**). **Group 2** cycled a more complex route featuring limited cycling infrastructure and a higher frequency of road crossings and potential

Fig. 1: The proposed methodological workflow, illustrating the completed stages of data collection, analysis and the envisioned future steps

hazards (**difficult route**). Based on the two scenarios, the following hypotheses were formulated:

- **Hypothesis 1: Low-stress Scenario:** The cyclist is in a relaxed state, which is characterised by lower physiological and self-reported stress, higher travel speed, and a narrower, more focused area of perception.
- **Hypothesis 2: High-stress Scenario:** The cyclist exhibits elevated stress levels, resulting in reduced travel speed and a wider, more vigilant and reduced area of perception.

Fig. 2: Data collection in Salzburg, Austria.

Fig. 3: Experimental Scenario. Each segment colour represents the frequency of detected Moment Of Stress (MOS) events based on physiological EDA data. Darker segments indicate a higher local concentration of stress events.

Each participant was equipped with wearable sensors to capture behavioural and physiological data. Eye movements and head orientation were recorded using the Pupil Labs Neon mobile eye tracking glasses, while physiological stress indicators, specifically EDA, were measured with the Empatica E4 wristband (4). An eDiary app (18) was used to synchronise wearable sensor measurements and smartphone-based GPS locations of participants. To complement objective measurements of stress events, self-reported feedback was gathered in post-hoc interviews.

The second step was to identify high-stress and low-stress cycling areas. Based on the methodology proposed by (16), we computed individualistic stress scores and MOS from frequency-filtered EDA measurements. We then spatially aggregated these measurements based on the approach of (9), where a buffer size of 20 metres was chosen to compute a ratio of detected stress points over all collected points (MOS Ratio). Spatial clusters of stress, i.e., hotspots and coldspots (shown in Figure 5), were identified based on the Getis-Ord G_i^* statistic.

The next step was the design of an agent-based simulation model to simulate cyclist behaviour within a virtual representation of the selected study areas. The model’s architecture and logic were structured based on a Unified Modeling Language (UML) diagram, which outlines the model initialisation and the iterative processes occurring at each time step. The implementation was done using the GAMA software, where both scenarios (described in the first step) were implemented in the simulation model. The virtual environment was enriched with street characteristics and building information excerpted from OpenStreetMap. The primary agent was defined as the moving cyclist whose behaviour is informed by empirically collected sensor data. The following sensor-based features provided the basis for implementing the agent’s behaviour:

- Perception area: the dynamic field of view of the agent (eye tracking)
- Direct line of view & direction of movement: vector-based properties guiding agent navigation (eye tracking)
- Stress levels: quantifiable based on electrodermal activity (EDA) (MOS score; (16))
- Driving speed: the velocity of the agent (GPS, eDiary app; (18))

Additionally, we adapted the perception area of the primary agent when approaching an intersection. 20 metres was used as the direct line of view, which was determined based on the work of von Stülpnagel (23), who identified the average sight vector length, defined as the distance between the cyclist’s body and a fixated object, to be 19.22 meters when approaching an intersection. While static infrastructure is captured by OSM data, dynamic obstacles need to be defined as additional agents. These were defined as abstract representations of other road users, i.e., cars, pedestrians, and other cyclists, acting as dynamic obstacles that are encountered by the primary agent. The model architecture was intentionally kept concise to focus on core functionalities, ensuring a robust foundation that can be expanded in future work.

To test whether the more difficult route was perceived as more stressful, we split the two tracks into equally spaced segments of 20 metres and computed

aggregate statistics (shown in Table 1) for the following attributes: MOS score, MOS events detected, and MOS ratio. We also calculated the average movement speed (m/s) of cyclists using GPS measurements. Self-reported stress ratings, collected in post-hoc interviews, were averaged for each route.

What remains missing in the methodological framework is to identify viewing behaviour in high-stress and low-stress areas, i.e., identified hotspots and coldspots, by combining fixations and gaze patterns with the dynamic features and distance to identified objects. For this, we plan to use a combination of computer vision-based depth estimation and panoptic segmentation (5; 22).

4 Results

Results of the pilot field study demonstrate different mobility experiences for the two groups/routes (Table 1). Participants reported feeling stressed more than twice as often on the difficult route (hypothesised as high-stress scenario) compared to the easy route (hypothesised as low-stress scenario), with a self-reported rating of **3.4** vs. **1.6** on a 5-point Likert scale. This was confirmed by objective physiological stress measurements; the average number of MOS detected per second and the average MOS score per metre were higher on the difficult route. Against our initial hypothesis, elevated stress levels did not affect the general cycling experience (**2.2** vs. **2.4** on a 5-point scale), confirming that qualitative surveys and interviews are highly subjective (11).

Table 1: Metrics indicating stress in both scenarios.

Variable	Group 1 (Easy Route)	Group 2 (Difficult Route)
Average MOS Score	0.102	0.095
MOS Ratio (non-MOS over MOS)	0.0173	0.0178
Average MOS Score per second	0.000072	0.000081
# MOS detected per second	0.0176	0.0196
Average MOS Score per metre	0.0000179	0.0000183
# MOS detected per metre	0.0043	0.0044
Average speed (m/s)	4.0	3.3
General experience (1–5)	2.2	2.4
How often stressed (1–5)	1.6	3.4

Although the experiment is based on two test scenarios (hypothesised as high-stress and low-stress routes), our spatial analysis reveals that stress events were not strictly confined to one route or the other. Instead, stress events frequently clustered at specific locations, i.e., high-traffic intersections, even on the easy route, indicating that local environmental and dynamic features, rather than overall route categorisation, were driving perceived stress.

By visualising spatial clusters of stress on top of the GPS tracks for the two routes, we observed that elevated stress occurs near intersections, at areas

with high traffic volumes, and segments of the route where dedicated cycling infrastructure is absent (Figure 5).

Fig. 4 displays the Pearson correlation matrix showing the linear dependence between physiological stress measurements, preliminary eye tracking metrics, and other features listed in Table 1. A correlation coefficient of $+0.85$ between *blink_counts* and the sum of detected MOS indicates a strong positive correlation between physiological stress and eye movement. Additionally, there is moderately positive correlations between other road users and blink count. Negative correlations were observed between average speed and MOS (-0.50), and between blink count and speed. This suggests that as cyclists' measured physiological stress levels increase, their average speed tends to decrease, while their blink count increases.

Fig. 4: Pearson correlation matrix showing dependencies between physiological stress (EDA-based MOS), behavioural (blink count), and contextual (speed, road user counts) features aggregated on 20 m road segments.

The analysis of viewing behaviour involving eye tracking data is still to be implemented, and we are currently experimenting with panoptic segmentation (for instance and semantic segmentation) and depth estimation for object detection (Fig. 6). By associating detected environmental objects with corresponding eye tracking metrics, we anticipate the following behavioural patterns: On the easy route, cyclists are expected to maintain longer forward fixation distances, enabling broader visual intake and facilitating a more exploratory riding experience. In contrast, on the difficult route, we expect a reduced forward field of view accompanied by more laterally distributed gaze patterns, reflecting increased visual scanning for potential hazards (14; 2).

Fig. 5: Moment of Stress (MOS) hotspots

5 Discussion and Outlook

This study demonstrated a proof-of-concept for integrating wearable sensors and agent-based modelling to quantify the link between the urban environment and cyclists' viewing behaviour under stress. Two routes of varying cycling infrastructure and stress potential were chosen as test areas for our study, where prelim-

inary findings confirm that inadequate cycling infrastructure with a higher frequency of road crossings and encountered obstacles such as other road users (*difficult route*) correlate with increased stress levels. This conclusion is supported by both objective sensor measurements and self-reported participant feedback.

The agent-based simulation environment is defined based on OSM data (roads and buildings) that were extracted for the two routes. Viewing behaviour of the primary agent was implemented based on findings of the literature (23), which changes with respect to obstacles encountered, and when approaching intersections. To further understand how stress affects cyclists’ viewing behaviour, physiological stress measurements need to be combined with attention-based interactions (eye tracking metrics) and computer vision-based analyses of first-person view videos. By aligning stress measurements, fixation and gaze metrics with static and dynamic elements captured from automated image analyses, changes in viewing behaviour under stressful cycling conditions can be related to spatiotemporal elements cyclists encounter on their trip. Figure 6 provides an example of our current work, relating computer vision-based object detection and depth estimation to cyclists’ fixation points.

Fig. 6: Ongoing research to relate viewing behaviour under stress to spatiotemporal surroundings based object detection (YOLOv5) and depth estimation (Depth-Anything)

As this is ongoing research, we acknowledge several limitations of our study. The limited geographic scope of the two study areas may not capture the full spectrum of spatiotemporal stress determinants encountered in active mobility. Similarly, the limited sample size (10 participants) of this pilot field study may not reflect the complete range of cyclist behaviours. Alternatively, we could have used findings from larger, existing studies that utilise wearable sensors. However, due to the individuality of study designs and methods, the limited sample sizes, and the geographic diversity of study areas, an objective comparison would have been challenging (11). Another limitation is ensuring behavioural fidelity, where realistic modelling of agent movement and dynamic interactions (e.g., governing how agents react to each other) is critical for the model’s validity. Future itera-

tions will focus on incorporating dynamic and naturalistic movement patterns, which are quantified through processing real-time video data with panoptic segmentation.

The primary contribution of this work is the methodological framework for evaluating cycling experiences based on empirically collected, multimodal sensor data, which can be integrated into an agent-based simulation framework for testing varying mobility conditions. We captured highly granular sensor data and translated it into a dynamic agent-based simulation model. Spatial clusters of physiological stress, i.e., hotspots, provide an objective assessment of (mobility) infrastructure, where identified stress clusters can serve as reference points for processing eye tracking metrics and for linking cyclists' viewing behaviour under stress to the spatiotemporal characteristics of their surrounding environment. The proposed agent-based simulation model provides an empirically informed and cost-effective virtual environment for evidence-based evaluation of urban mobility design. Ultimately, this study underscores the immense potential of multimodal sensor data, people-centred approaches to urban mobility planning, and applying spatial data science to create intuitively safe and sustainable active mobility environments.

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